

Complexation of some transition metal ions with 1,2,2-trimethyl-1,3-cyclopentanedicarboxylate and CDTA

M. P. Kaur^a, B. K. Kanungo^{a*} and J. S. Sandhu^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sant Longowal Institute of Engineering and Technology, Longowal-148 106, India

E-mail : b.kanungo@vsnl.com Fax : 91-1672-3280057

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002, India

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Complexation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} involving CDTA (*trans*-1,2-dinitrilocyclohexanetetraacetic acid) and 1,2,2-trimethyl-1,3-cyclopentanedicarboxylate (camphorate) has been studied by pH-metric method. The formation constants are determined at ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 M$ and 27° in aqueous medium. The order of stability in mixed ligand complexes is Co^{II} < Ni^{II} > Cu^{II} < Zn^{II}.

Chelates of polyaminocarboxylates like EDTA (ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid), DTPA (diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid), HEDTA (*N*-hydroxyethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) and CDTA are well known for their use in analytical chemistry¹. Also, CDTA forms 10 to 10³ times more stable complexes than commonly used EDTA. Formation of mixed ligand complexes of some transition metal and lanthanide ions containing CDTA and thioglycolic, thiomaleic acid or norleucinate have already been reported². 1,2,2-Trimethyl-1,3-cyclopentanedicarboxylate (camphorate) is a ligand with versatile utility³. Its complexes with some transition metal and lanthanide ions are known⁴, but little work has been done to study the complexation in a mixed ligand system where the second ligand was 1,10-phenanthroline⁵ or DTPA⁶. The present work is focussed on the study of mixed ligand complexes containing 1,2,2-trimethyl-1,3-cyclopentanedicarboxylate and CDTA with some transition metal ions.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that the mixed ligand complex formation curve is superimposed on the primary complex curve at low pH and diverges after pH ~2.8, ~2.6, ~2.9 and ~3.1 in Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} systems, respectively, which indicates that the coordination of secondary ligand with the [M(CDTA)] complex starts from this region onwards according to the reaction (charges are omitted for clarity),

The values of \bar{n}_{mix} (average number of secondary ligands attached to the primary complex) and free ligand exponent (pL_{mix}) were calculated and formation curves (Fig. 1) were plotted. The formation curves were extended between 0 and 0.970, which confirm the formation of 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand

Fig. 1. Formation curves of M-CDTA-camphorate (M = Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}) systems

complex. For mixed ligand complexes, precipitation was observed at pH 9.12 (Co^{II}), 8.76 (Ni^{II}), 8.65 (Cu^{II}) and 9.22 (Zn^{II}), whereas for the binary complexes precipitation was observed at pH 6.91, 6.84, 4.51 and 7.71 respectively for Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} in the reaction mixture. A considerable shift in the pH of precipitation as compared to binary complexes also confirms the formation of ternary complexes. Spectroscopic studies indicate that after pH ~3, with the increase of pH, the intensity of the peak at 737 nm increases, which shows the increase in complex species with the increase of pH. At pH ~6.5, there is sudden decrease in intensity and shift in band; this may be due to appearance of species caused by polymerization or hydroxo-complex formation near this pH. The absence of any polymerized or hydroxo-complex in the complex formation region, i.e. from pH ~3 to ~6.4, was confirmed by the method, described by Carey and Martell⁷, according to which in case of hydrolysis and polymerization a straight line plot is obtained for $\bar{n}_{mix}/[L_{mix}]$ vs $[L_{mix}]$. In the present case, the plots are smooth

Table 1. Logarithms of stability constants of ternary complexes of some transition metal ions with camphoric acid and CDTATemp. = 27°, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

Complex	Method		
	Half-integral	Pointwise	Graphical
Co ^{II}	3.294	3.306 ± 0.08	3.30
Ni ^{II}	3.336	3.350 ± 0.07	3.35
Cu ^{II}	3.319	3.332 ± 0.1	3.33
Zn ^{II}	3.239	3.241 ± 0.02	3.25

curves, confirming the absence of hydroxo and polynuclear species. The formation constants ($\log \beta_{\text{mix}}$) calculated from \bar{n}_{mix} and pL_{mix} by different methods are presented in Table 1. The values of $\log \beta_{\text{mix}}$ for Cu-CDTA-camphorate (3.325 ± 0.002) calculated from spectral data is consistent with the results obtained from pH-metric method. No suitable data were obtained for the mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} for calculation by spectrophotometric method.

The order of stability in terms of metal ions is Co^{II} < Ni^{II} > Cu^{II} < Zn^{II}. The values of $\log \beta_{\text{mix}}$ for Cu^{II} is low as compared to that of Ni^{II}. This deviation can be explained on the basis of tetragonal distortion for the Cu^{II} complex, with a d^9 -configuration and steric effect caused due to introduction of the secondary ligand. Due to the Jahn-Teller distortion, it is expected that CDTA will occupy three equatorial positions and one axial position and the secondary ligand has to occupy the remaining positions, one necessarily along the Z-axis. Thus the secondary ligand has to cover a greater span and may be strained contributing to lower stability. Similar results were also obtained by Chitambam and Bhattacharya⁸ for Cu-NTA/EDTA-L complexes. It is interesting to note that the stability constants of mixed ligand complexes are higher than that of binary camphorate complexes, which indicates that the mixed ligand complexes are more favorably formed than the complex containing only one type of ligand. However, for complexes of lanthanide with same pair of ligands are less stable than their binary complexes⁹. This may be due to the small size of the transition metal ions as compared to the lanthanide ions. When the size of the metal ion is small there will be more repulsions between bulky groups of ligand, and metal ion would prefer to bind with the other ligand than to bind with the more groups of the same ligand. Hence it will preferably form mixed ligand complexes. These complexes (M-CDTA-camphorate) were found to be less stable than the complexes where DTPA and EDTA⁹ were used instead of CDTA. This may be due to greater stability of M-CDTA complexes as compared to the M-EDTA and M-DTPA complexes. This

evidence that if the primary complex is more stable it will not easily make a free site for coordination of second ligand.

The complexes of CDTA in solution have been investigated¹⁰ by ¹H NMR spectroscopy and reported that CDTA be have as pentadentate ligand with one free carboxylate group. Since the most common coordination number is six for these metal ions, it is assumed that when camphorate coordinates with M-CDTA, it either replaces one of the carboxylate groups of CDTA and one water molecule or coordinates as a monodentate ligand through one of its carboxylate groups. Molecular modeling was carried out for the complexes (with Ni^{II} as a representative metal ion) with both the possibilities and it was found that the former (strain energy = 112.9454 kcal mol⁻¹) was more stable than the latter (strain energy = 123.459 kcal mol⁻¹). Thus the mixed ligand complexes may have distorted octahedral geometry with four sites occupied by CDTA and two by camphorate ions. Other complexes may have similar geometry except for Cu^{II}, where the bond length along the z-axis would be higher due to Jahn-Teller distortion.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade (Fluka/IRE/E. Merck). Solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving their chloride salts and their concentrations verified spectrophotometrically. Stock solutions of CDTA and camphoric acid were prepared by dissolving their sodium salts/acid in triple-distilled water and their concentrations were verified potentiometrically. Sodium perchlorate monohydrate was extracted pure by recrystallization from water. NaOH solution used was carbonate-free¹¹.

A Hanna HI 8418 pH meter (with precision 0.01 pH) assembled with combined glass electrode and calomel electrode (HI 1131) was used. Titrations of (a) HClO₄; (b) HClO₄, camphoric acid (L₂) and metal ion (M : L₂, 1 : 1); (c) HClO₄, CDTA (L₁) and metal ion (M : L₁, 1 : 1); and (d) HClO₄, CDTA, metal ion and camphoric acid (M : L₁ : L₂, 1 : 1 : 1) were carried out against standard sodium hydroxide at 27° and at a fixed ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M$ NaClO₄). The solutions were protected from atmospheric carbon dioxide via a nitrogen blanket. From the titration data the calculations of formation constants were carried out using computer program written in FORTRAN-77⁹. UV-visible spectra were recorded on a Uvikon-930 spectrophotometer. Absorption spectra of reaction mixtures were measured as a function of pH and stability constants were determined by computer program SPECFIT¹². Molecular modeling calculations were carried out using software package HYPERCHEM¹³.

References

1. R. S. Juang and I. P. Huang, *Inst. Engg. Chem. Res.*, 2000, **39**, 1409; S. Karabulut, A. Karabakan, A. Denizli and Y. Yurum, *Sep. Purification Tech.*, 2000, **18**, 177; R. A. Bulman, *Struct. Bonding*, 1987, **67**, 91.
2. H. S. Rana and J. P. Tandon, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 279; B. C. Dash, P. K. Tripathy and B. K. Kanungo, *Montsh. Chem.*, 1991, **122**, 341; N. P. Jena, M. Baral and B. K. Kanungo, *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1993, **65**, 11.
3. "The Condensed Chemical Dictionary", ed. A. E. Rose, 7th ed., Renold, New York, 1966; H. Urabe, T. Yamakawa and F. Sato, *Tetrahedron Assym.*, 1992, **39**, 5.
4. M. R. King and G. W. Everett, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 1237; M. Xianxian, W. Jigui, D. Ruwen, Y. Kaling and Z. Zhongsheng, *Chin. Sci. Bull.*, 1990, **35**, 38.
5. S. Zhongxing, Y. Sheng, Z. Zhengzhi and D. Ruwen, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1997, **106**, 261.
6. M. P. Kaur, B. K. Kanungo and J. S. Sandhu, *J. Indian Council Chem.*, 1999, **16**, 7.
7. G. H. Carey and A. E. Martell, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 32.
8. M. V. Chitambam and P. K. Bhattacharya, *Chim. Hung.*, 1973, **75**, 123.
9. M. P. Kaur, Ph.D. Thesis, Punjabi University, 2000.
10. B. Jezowska-Tizebiatowska, L. Latos-Grazynski and H. Kozlowski, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1977, **21**, 245; L. Latos-Grazynski and B. Jezowska-Tizebiatowska, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 1249.
11. A. I. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1989.
12. H. Gampp, M. Meader, C. J. Meyer and A. D. Zuberhuhler, *Talanta*, 1982, **32**, 1133.
13. "Computational Chemistry", Manual for HYPERCHEM version 3, Hypercube Inc., Waterloo.